

Effect of Teachers' Motivation on their Working Performance. Comparing Boarding School and Twelve Years' Basic Education in Rwanda

NSHIMIYIMANA Gaston

Article in University Of Kigali (UOK), October, 2022

Abstract: The study aims at assessing “the effects of teachers' motivation to their working performance”. Then this study has been conducted in Burera district, with study questions like Investigate the effects of hygienic factors, effects of motivating factors, and effects of teachers competences on teachers' working performance in boarding and Twelve years' basic education schools in Burera district/ Rwanda Compare the effect of teachers' motivation on working performance among boarding and Twelve years' schools in Burera district/Rwanda where data have been collected by using questionnaires, interviews, class observations and document review to find related answers. the total population estimated to be 83 composed by 70 and 13 administrators from GS Butete and E.S Kagogo as schools in Burera district /Rwanda. The results found out in the boarding school indicated that 65.9% of the variation in dependent variables (teachers working performance) can be explained by motivator factors, hygienic factors and teachers' competences have positive significance effect of teachers' performance. The results found out in 12YBES indicated that 98.6 % of the variation in dependent variables (teachers working performance) can be explained by hygienic motivator factors and teachers' competences have positive significance effect on teachers' performance. The results found out in the table indicated that 96.5% of the variation in dependent variables (teachers working performance) can be explained by teachers' competences, means that there is positive significance effect on teachers' performance. Based on the findings about inequality of teaching and learning condition I request to the government of Rwanda to ensure equal caring teachers either from boarding or 12YBES and providing enough school requirement that will increase the chance of increasing teachers working performance

I. INTRODUCTION

This research indicated that teachers' motivation generally promote their level of participation in the teaching activities. It is clear that a motivated teacher will work harder, develop new techniques and activities, and in general reinforced for developing the learners' opportunities that develop his/her career (Gokce, 2010). As a teacher, it is better to be intrinsically and extrinsically to spearhead motivation and satisfaction to teachers in order to maintain the motivation to teach over the course of one's career. Teachers' motivation is relying on different factors, including compensation, success in the classroom, their

recognition, the training they receive and the prospect of promotion and career advancement (Sah, 2016). A study of determining influence of motivator, hygienic factors and teachers' competences are, therefore, paramount as motivation is the trigger force behind all actions the teachers take at workplace. While most studies on teacher motivation have been centered in secondary and university settings, as it appears that few studies have been done on teacher motivation, especially in Rwanda context. The main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of teachers' motivation to their working performance in twelve years' basic education like G.S Butete and boarding school like E.S Kagogo in Burera district/ Rwanda.

According to (Herzberg ,1968) reported by (Rikard Dahlberg, 2015), revealed that Herzberg's two factors theory focusing on intrinsic and extrinsic motivation applied on teachers to work effectively, emphasized that different factors in working environment are considered to create satisfaction (motivation) on teachers in order to strive for better performance and prevent dissatisfaction in their working site. Also stated that when teachers are motivated help them to enhance their performance. According to Abraham Maslow (1908-1970) reported by (R. H. M. Fallatah and J. Syed ,2018) indicated the motivation into five needs and arranging these hierarchical order of importance to employees, which are **physiological need** (via such as food, water and breathing. Employees who have physiological needs that they seek to satisfy and are specifically necessary for their motivation at work **Security** (safety needs such as financial safety and safety against redundancy and harm) At this second level security is major pursuit needs such as a fear of job instability by (Aworemi et al.2011, Khan et al.2011) reported by R. H. M. Fallatah and J. Syed ,2018) this needs are helpful for employees to achieve the organizational activities when this needs are not provided the working intention can't be achieved then perturbed the target of organization.

Social needs are the need for love, friendship, acceptance and belongingness The absence of friend ship, encouragement and support of fellow workers and managers makes the employee feel motivated, as never before, to attain this need with great intensity, so, love and belongingness become the paramount need for the employee at work and help to accomplish the available tasks in accurate manner Esteem and autonomy ,(the need for respect, appreciation ,empowerment and being given a voice and right **Esteem needs** indicate a need to respect one's rights, appreciation of one's ability and capacity, acknowledgement of one's achievement and recognition of

one's autonomy and independence by (Anyim et al.2012), **Self - actualization**, is the highest needs which entire doing and achieving one's best potential, indicated that fulfillment of employees needs play great role in context of their performance because the employees needs are the core

motivators to empower their performance in their assigned activities. This needs are needed by teachers to reach their full potential.

Fig. 1: Indicating Maslow hierarchy needs

This research is indicating teacher's motivation as teachers with elaborate working conditions, means that they attend jobs at time being courageous and increase working efforts in their daily activities, Ozbilen et al, (2020). While working performance refers to how teachers stimulate the success of schools and elaborate general opportunities to all school beneficiaries economically, socially and politically in context of educational development to enhance required competent skilled labors market to act in different domains Baris Yildis, Gokhan Gunay, and Fatih Mutlu Ozbilen,2020). This research if aiming to enhance educational development which will base on equal share and providing the same opportunities both in 12 YBE and Boarding schools that will boost up general required competency, skills and knowledge for future worldwide life success.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Concept of motivation and teacher working performance

(Jeenvan, 2017) revealed that teachers are motivated when they are advantaged to create innovation to improve education quality and willingly to create institutional solutions of existing challenges and problems. According to (Weinstein and C.R DeHaan,2014) teachers' motivation are ways in which teachers at work place initiating and directing their school activities through energize behavior, generate and increase tasks engagement, and direct actions towards certain ends or goals. As noted above according to (Nathan C. Hall &Thomas Goetz,2013), motivation is assumed to result from personal evaluations of the desirability and expectations regarding the feasibility of the options for actions, these stable motivational tendencies and beliefs delivered from interests, goal orientations, and assumptions about one's personal capabilities.

In context of school teachers have both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation, is hedonistic preference, self- serving for one's own fulfillment of one being or wellbeing of another (Antoinette Weibel, Meike wiemann &Margit osterlon, 2014). intrinsic motivation whenever employees regulate their emotions for the scale pleasure of regulating them. There is no contingency or rewards linked with the behavior, and individual acts for the interests, challenges, or their pressure or regulating emotions. In the content of emotional labor, expressing an authentic smile can be easily seen as intrinsically act (Michel. Cossette, 2014). While Extrinsic motivation, is external incentives for the individuals (awards or penalties). There makes mediated satisfaction possible, especially by the means of money (Antoinette Weibel, Meike wiemann &Margit osterlon, 2014). Is form of motivation in which teachers act to feel worth and to preserve their self -esteem provided from external pressure introjection implies a pressure that comes from within the persons (Michel, cossette,2014). Extrinsic motivation requires the presence of stimulus in order for the behavior to occur. The stimulus is typically in form of a reward for performing work safety or a negative consequences when work is not performed safety, should be involvement of bonus, pressure from external agencies such as professional associations. According to Ozbilen et al, (2020) motivated teachers are the ones who elaborate their working conditions, means that they attend jobs at time being courageous and increase working efforts in their daily activities, always are alert to discover and develop school opportunities in which the success is attained.

Herzberg’s Motivation Theory (external and intrinsic motivation) into forms of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation which rely on different factors, motivators factors, such as achievements, recognition advancement, growth, while Hygienic factors include company policies supervision, relationships, work conditions remunerations, salary and security. The motivation is how workers needs are satisfied included, their interest in, challenging work and available friendly coworkers, opportunities for growth, high respects

and high trust at work place. (HartHolzberger,2022) revealed that teacher motivation indicated by involvement of heterogeneous higher order construct that subsumes a different of constructs like self- efficacy, enthusiasm, goal - orientation, interest, self-regulatory skills and autonomous motivation that encourage personal mind to achieve duties. According to (Herzberg ,1968) reported by (Rikard Dahlberg, 2015), Herzberg categorized motivation.

Fig. 2: Indicating interworking of Herzberg theory (extrinsic and intrinsic motivation)

This implies that Factors related to dissatisfaction come to be called “hygiene factors” based on how covered work environment. Means that the motivators aim to create satisfaction and motivation when they exist, but not dissatisfaction if they are not present. The present of hygiene factors prevents dissatisfaction but they do not necessarily create satisfaction. Hygiene factors are company policy, supervision and relationship, working conditions, salaries, security while motivators factors are achievement recognition, interesting works, increased responsibility and advancement and growth that increase the workers’ efforts of insolvent in activity performance, in absence of these factors teachers’ performance become very low.

B. Effects of teachers’ competences on their working performance

According to (M. Mulder and J. Winterton 2017) revealed that World Wide competence based education gained much interest as innovation to prepare more effectively for superior performance to overcome the barriers between the World of education and the work and to align the educational programs in vocational profession and high education to the labor markets needs and educational development in society. Professional competence of teachers is seen as thee generic integrated and internalized capability to deliver sustainable effective performance including problem solving, realizing innovation and creating transformation in educational domain argued by (M. Vonken, 2017). According to A.T .Evers and B.I.J.M. Vander, Heijok (2017) indicated that

competence indicate a teachers no longer depends on rules guide lines, has an intuitive grip of situations established on deep understanding , has analytical methods used only in new situations and has a vision of what is possible in achieving the school duties to enhance developed education.

C. Effects of Motivator factors to teachers working performance

(Eduward L. Deci and Richard M. Ryan,2014) revealed that when teachers ’s basic psychological needs are satisfied in the working place they are more autonomously motivated to work, and when their basic needs are thwarted they are controlled or a motivated when at work. Autonomous motivation, which recruits the whole- hearted efforts of teachers to perform better the school activities, has payoffs in terms of productivity, creativity, and lower burnout and turnover.

(R. Chard M. Ryan & Eduward L. Deci, 2017) revealed that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation favor employees’ / teachers performance because there is links the individuals, effective and efficiency performance of their assigned activities. Motivation must consider how the characteristics of an activity and context are experienced and engaged in by individuals in question. the teachers at schools will be intrinsically and extrinsically motivated for different activities to the degree that he or she finds inherently interesting and enjoyable, which is in turn a junction of proximal to basic need satisfactions.

Use of controls to motivate performance on an interesting or complex activity seems to lead teachers to narrow their focus and take a shortcut to the extrinsic outcome rather than taking interest in and having a full engagement with the activity itself. (B. Baris Yildis, Gokhan Gunay, and Fatih Mutlu Ozbilen,2020) indicated that teacher motivation serves as an umbrella for innovations in teaching and learning process, which stimulate the success of schools in context of educational development to enhance required competent skilled labors market.

(Alena Agullar, 2018) revealed that educational institution the first things to cater for are micro, social, political and economic issues in the context of school societies, where teachers must be efficiently paid (offering salaries) and socially treated as people who can influence the development of institutions, by addressing racism, classism and sexism that exist in his/her society and taken as the motivation that prompt effective working in order to enhance efficient productivity. Head teachers at schools have to emphasis on teachers social wellbeing to care through caring them strongly to be healthy that bring jo to employees lives and build empathy for each other that help boost up the performance of in institution to fulfill its objectives. (S-Jonson, Reimer Terwindt, James Townsend and Sharath Jeevan, 2017) indicated that to improve teachers' incentives is related to encouragement their selves – efficiency, commitment to perform school assigned duties that facilitate accurate accomplishment of school goals hence wellbeing of institutions.

III. THE STUDY

A. Study population

Kumar. R, (2011) defined population as the totality of persons or objects which a study is concerned. In this study the population was comprised by 60 people of G.S Butete both teachers and school administrators' staffs and of 23 people of E.S Kagogo both teachers, and school administrators' staffs. Researcher choose this population because they realize that both staffs are involved day to day teaching activities.

B. The research methodology

In this study summarize the tools and techniques that have been used to investigate the effects of teachers' motivation on their working performance especially in G.S

Butete as 12 YBE and E.S Kagogo as Boarding school. The survey method is appropriate as it indicating the development of questionnaire based on different teachers' motivational elements indicated in literature review.

C. Tools and instruments for Data collection

The instruments that will be used for the purpose of the study are questionnaires and interviews in hand of primary data and documentation in hand secondary data. The questions for people will be issued in accordance with the research work and the research questions and will be framed in a way that it would not be misunderstood by the respondents.

➤ *Questionnaires*

The researcher has been use an open- ended question for giving the space explanation to the respondents where there is information that will not be mentioned in questioned in the questionnaires. The closed ended questions have been used. The questionnaire used to gather data for this study was adapted from the Teacher Motivation and Job Satisfaction Survey by Mertler (2001). The respondents are asked to indicate their level of motivation to 17 motivational factors, using a fivepoint Likert scale of Poorly motivated = 1, Slightly motivated =2, Neutral = 3, Motivated = 4 and Strongly motivated = 5.

➤ *Interview*

Interview is a conversion between two or more people, where interviewer asked questions to interviewee. This is helpful in obtaining deeply views of teachers, and students related to the issue. Interview involves face to face discussions between the research and respondents therefore it gives a researcher an opportunity to penetrate further and keep the responses on the issue of interest. This method is a complement to the questionnaires because it helps to collect the information that questionnaire cannot collect.

➤ *Documentation*

D uring the collection for secondary data, a researcher read the different documents related to the research purpose those are concerning to the school report describing the annual teachers working performance based on school imihigo program where all teachers at particular school has a file indicating his/ her teaching performance at the end of year indicated by given imihigo marks given by Head teacher's school, the marks given for teachers are basement to be given annual working bonus.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	2.644	3	.881	12.257	.000 ^b
1 Residual	1.366	19	.072		
Total	4.010	22			

Table 1: Analysis of variance of motivator factors, hygienic factors and teachers' competences on their working performance in boarding school (E.S KAGOGO)

a. Dependent Variable: T.W.P

b. Predictors: (Constant), T.C, Hygienic, Motivator

The table 1 indicated that there is significance relationship between motivator factors hygienic factors and teachers' competences in Rwandan government aided schools. This implies that null hypothesis is rejected while alternative hypothesis is accepted. Here there is significance relationship between motivator factors, hygienic factor and teachers' competences on teachers working performance.

This implies that one unit of change in independent variables (Motivator factors, hygienic factors and teachers' competences) decrease dependent variable (teachers working performance) by 4.010 Regression analysis on both motivator factors, hygienic factors and teachers' competences on their working performance in twelve years' basic education (GS BUTETE)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.993 ^a	.987	.986	.07819

Table 2: Model summary of motivator factors, hygienic factors and teachers' competences

a. Predictors: (Constant), T.C, Motivator, Hygienic

The table 2: indicated that 98.7% variation in dependent variable (teachers working performance) can be explained by motivators factors, hygienic factors and

teachers' competences and remaining percentage can be attributed to other variables which are not explained in this model.

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	26.047	3	8.682	1420.273	.000
1 Residual	.342	56	.006		b
Total	26.389	59			

Table 3: Analysis of variance of motivator factors, hygienic factors and teachers' competences on their working performance in twelve years' basic education (GS BUTETE)

a. Dependent Variable: T.W.P

b. Predictors: (Constant), T.C, Motivator, Hygienic

The table 3 indicated that there is significance relationship between motivator factors hygienic factors and teachers competences in Rwandan government aided schools .This implies that null hypothesis is rejected while alternative hypothesis is accepted .Here there is significance relationship between motivator factors , hygienic factor and teachers' competences on teachers The table 4 indicated that there are positive effects among

motivator factors, hygienic factors and teachers' competences on teachers working performance. This implies that one unit of change in independent variables (Motivator factors, hygienic factors and teachers' competences) decrease dependent variable (teachers working performance) by.26.389 Comparing the effects of teachers' motivation to their working performance between twelve years' basic education and boarding school.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.993 ^a	.987	.986	.07819

Table 4: Model summary of motivator factors, hygienic factors and teachers' competences (T.C) on teachers working performance in Twelve years' basic education (12YBEs) GS BUTETE

a. Predictors: (Constant), T.C, Motivator, Hygienic

KAGOGO Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.812 ^a	.659	.606	.26813

a. Predictors: (Constant), T.C, Hygienic,

Motivator Based on the findings obtained from the collected data in both schools G.S BUTETE as Twelve years basic education and E.S Kagogo as boarding school indicating that the teachers motivation are not the same where in boarding schools teachers are cared in terms of hygienic factors, motivator factors and their selves competences like availability of school materials , such as books , effective working environment and school bonus and different reward based on their working performance at school that prompt them to work hardly and affect teachers working performance at level of 81.2 % .

AS indicate by table6 ,while in Twelve years basic education the teachers motivation is still low to manage the working performance of teachers for example : the schools learning and teaching materials , like books , class looms , chairs are less than the students the schools holding , the school environment is not conducive due to less recreation facilities to ensure extra-curricular that led to difficulties in content delivery procedure , about teachers bonus the teachers are not permitted to acquire bonus differ from boarding teachers who acquire bonus . This implies that the decrease of teachers' motivation / demotivation of teachers lead to discouragement in working condition or teachers working performance in level of 98.4%. which is taken as serious challenge in academic performance

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Introduction

This chapter comprises summary of research objectives and research question, research methodology which was used by the researcher while conducting this study it also contains summary of presentation, analysis and interpretation and information collected from the research site and finally, the summary, conclusion, recommendation and suggestion for further study . This study had specific objectives such as to investigate the effects of hygienic factors on teachers' working performance in selected schools in Burera district, to analyze the effects of motivator factors on teachers' performance in selected schools in Burera district and to determine the effects of teachers' competences on their working performance in selected schools in Burera district. All of these objectives described above their summary are explained below.

B. Summary of findings

The findings from the objective number one which called to investigate the effects of hygienic factors on teachers' working performance in G.S Butete and E.S Kagogo. As in G.S Butete results indicated that there is positive and significance effects of hygienic factors on teachers working performance in government aided schools. (R=0.987) and P value (0.00) while in E.S Kagogo (0.987) and P value (000). This implies that hygienic factors are availability in boarding school that help improve teachers working performance as to fulfill the objective one Means that null of hypothesis was rejected and alternative hypothesis were accepted this is similar to the study of Bailey (2005) who indicated that there is positive and significance effects of hygienic factors on teachers

performance in government aided schools because when teachers are given this supports either school equipment increase of salary help teachers to enjoy good life and encourage them to work that increase their working performance . Other researcher such as ((Deci&Tracy,2011) revealed that when teachers are exposed to work contexts that foster decision making discretion creates an opportunity for teachers to feel more control of their works and to exercise choices about what to do and how to do it. Decision making discretion at work place provides teachers freedom and choices about to do their works rather than being externally controlled, regulated or pressured.

The findings from the objective number two which called to investigate the effects of motivator factors on teachers' working performance in especially in E.S Kagogo as government aided school, the study concluded that there is positive and significant effect of motivator factors on teachers working performance in Rwandan government aided schools.(R=.732) and P value (0.00) while in G.S Butete study concluded that there is positive and significant effect of motivator factors on teachers working performance in Rwandan government aided schools. (R= .940) and P value (0.00) that bring positive results to answer the research question two relating to how motivator factors influence teachers working performance. This means that motivator factors affect teachers working performance these findings have similarity of the research made by (MINEDUC, 2016) identifies that effective system of school monitoring improve the quality of teaching and reinforces responsibilities for creating working conditions that lead to fulfillment of the school goals that indicating the effects of motivator factors on teachers working performance.

The findings from the objective number three which called to investigate the effects of teachers' competences on their working performance. Especially in E.S Kagogo as government aided schools. The study concluded that there are positive and significant effects of teachers' competences in Rwandan government aided schools. (R=.795) and P value (0.00) as indicated that there is significant effects of teachers competence on working performance, where teachers are competent at work that improve development of school to fulfill the school objectives. while in G.S Butete The study concluded that there are positive and significant effects of teachers' competences in Rwandan government aided schools. (R=.993) and P value (000) this indicating that low level of teachers' competences decrease the level of teachers' performance that provide real information on how teachers competence is required to boost up teachers working performance. This means that teachers' competences affect teachers working performance, these findings have similarity of the research made by(UNESCO,2017) in global education monitoring report to increase teacher competency, the school are engaged to be empowered to monitor and develop and support their schools through delivering trainings where they acquire skills to support the CPD of their teaching staff and to plan for school improvement and development. These help

teachers to perform better the lessons rather than those who do not have competences.

C. Conclusion

Basing on the findings of the study, the effects of teachers' motivation on their working performance in Rwandan schools especially in G.S Butete and E.S Kagogo indicate that motivator factors, hygienic factors and teachers' competences have significance relationship with teachers working performance in Rwandan schools especially GS Butete and E.S Kagogo in Burera district since none research questions have been tested negatively means that all alternatives were accepted. Promoted the objectives of this research because the researcher come up with the conclusion that there is significance relationship between teachers' motivation and teachers working performance as indicated by other researchers such as (VVOB, 2017), argued that the government, therefore, recognizes that the motivated teacher is the main instrument in bringing about the desired improvements in quality learning ,2017). (B. Baris Yildis, Gokhan Gunay, and Fatih Mutlu Ozbilen,2020) indicated that teacher motivation serves as an umbrella for innovations in teaching and learning process, which stimulate the success of schools in context of educational development to enhance required competent skilled labors market. This research will let government, school managers to understand the role of teachers 'motivation on their working performance.

D. Recommendation

As this study is academic and also have revealed many important findings in academic field , government and partners of education system were recommended to equally sharing the school equipment because referring in boarding schools the school equipment are enough ratio with the school staffs and learners available while in twelve years the school equipment are not matching with number of school staffs and available learners and in other hand about teachers bonus the 12 YBE (twelve years basic education there is no confirmed bonus differ from boarding school where bonus is accepted for teachers) that indicating the inequality and careless of ministry of education in Rwanda, that discourage 12 YBES to work un properly different to Boarding schools where teachers are motivated to work. That why this is advocacy to cater for these issues and that will increase equal chance about teachers working conditions for both Rwandan teachers with no consideration of their different working schools

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